

Anomaly-based Web Application Firewall using HTTP-specific features and One-Class SVM

Nico Epp¹, Ralf Funk¹, Cristian Cappelletti¹

¹ Facultad Politécnica – Universidad Nacional de Asunción
San Lorenzo – Paraguay

{nicoeppfriesen,ralffunk0}@gmail.com, ccappo@pol.una.py

Abstract. *Vulnerabilities in web applications pose great risks because they can be exploited by malicious attackers through the Internet. Web Application Firewalls placed in front of these applications can help to minimize these risks. In this paper, we present such a firewall based on anomaly detection that aims to detect anomalous HTTP requests using One-Class SVM classifier. Our work uses expert knowledge about the HTTP request structure to build feature extraction methods that improve the detection rates. We include a link to the online repository that contains the code of our implementation for the purpose of reproducibility and extensibility. With extensive experimental testing in a public dataset, we validate the competitiveness of our WAF presented here. These tests show that our WAF reaches an average of F1-score of 0.95 also show that the detection process of our implementation should not have a noticeable effect on the response time of the protected applications. Besides, the WAF can be trained with a considerable amount of normal messages in a matter of a few minutes. Finally, the source code of our implementation is available in our public repository, so that others may reproduce our results and extend our work with further research.*

Resumen. *Las vulnerabilidades en las aplicaciones web contienen gran riesgo ya que ellas pueden ser explotadas por atacantes maliciosos a través de Internet. Los cortafuegos para aplicaciones web (WAF) pueden ser colocados frente a estas aplicaciones de modo a ayudar a minimizar estos riesgos. En este artículo, presentamos un WAF basado en detección por anomalías que ayuda a detectar peticiones HTTP anómalas utilizando un clasificador One-Class SVM. Nuestro trabajo utiliza conocimiento de expertos sobre la estructura de las peticiones HTTP de forma a construir métodos de extracción de características que mejoran el ratio de detección. Incluimos un enlace a un repositorio en línea que contiene el código de nuestra implementación para facilitar la reproducibilidad y extensibilidad. Con un extensivo conjunto de pruebas experimentales sobre una base de datos pública, validamos la competitividad de nuestro WAF presentado aquí. Estas pruebas muestran que nuestro WAF alcanza un valor promedio de 0.95 en la medida F1 y también que el proceso de detección de nuestra implementación no debe tener un efecto notable en el tiempo de respuesta de las aplicaciones web protegidas. Además, nuestro WAF puede ser entrenado con una cantidad considerable de mensajes normales en cuestión de pocos minutos. Finalmente, el código fuente de nuestra implementación está disponible en un*

repositorio público, de esta manera otros pueden reproducir nuestros resultados y extender nuestro trabajo con nuevas investigaciones.

Keywords: *Web Attacks Detection, Anomaly-based WAF, One-Class SVM, HTTP features.*

1. Introduction

Web applications have become mainstream in the last decade. Their vulnerabilities pose a great risk because they can easily be exploited by malicious attackers through the Internet. Web Application Firewalls (WAF) can be placed in front of these applications to minimize the risk of attacks [Torrano-Giménez 2015].

According to the detection method, a WAF can be either *misuse-based*, when it looks for known attack signatures, or *anomaly-based*, when it aims to differentiate between normal and anomalous HTTP requests, where the anomalies can include malicious attacks [Torrano-Giménez 2015].

In order to accomplish this differentiation task, the WAF needs to recognize characteristics about the individual HTTP requests. This kind of WAF has two phases, namely training and detection. During the training phase, it extracts models from observed normal requests. During the detection phase, it compares the incoming requests to these models and flags them as anomalous if they deviate significantly from normal requests previously seen. A great strength of this approach lies with the fact that the WAF only needs to be retrained if there are changes in the applications it protects and not because of the appearance of new attacks [Kruegel and Vigna 2003].

For the anomaly detection process of the WAF, one possible strategy is to face it as a classification problem with a single known class, denominated One Class Classification (OCC) problem [Khan and Madden 2014]. This way the normal HTTP requests belong to this single known class and all the anomalies will be categorized as not belonging to this class. This OCC approach has the advantage of not needing labeled anomalous data for training, only normal requests are required.

One methodology to solve OCC problems is to employ tools from the area of Machine Learning, one of those being the One-Class SVM, which has been used with great success for this kind of problems [Khan and Madden 2014]. The characteristics of HTTP requests need to be expressed as numeric feature vectors in order to be used by this classifier.

In this article, we present a WAF based on anomaly detection that uses features selected with expert knowledge about HTTP requests together with One-Class SVM classifier to detect anomalous requests.

This article is organized as follows: In Section 2 we present related works. The concepts about feature selection and One-Class SVM are presented in Section 3. We describe our proposed WAF in Section 4. Section 5 presents experiments, results and comparison with other works and we finish this paper with conclusions and ideas for future work in Section 6.

2. Related works

In [Kruegel and Vigna 2003] and [Kruegel et al. 2005] the authors use expert knowledge about the structure of HTTP requests in their anomaly detection system. They describe how the query string of an HTTP request consists of an ordered list of n pairs of parameters and their corresponding values and how they use statistical methods to build anomaly models of the values for each of the parameters. Some of the models they use are the length of the values, their character distribution, structural inference, parameter presence, among others. For example, one of their models describes the string length of the different values that appear for the parameter *username* in the URL */login*. The approach of these authors differs from ours in that they use statistical methods to detect anomalous requests while we employ One-Class SVM.

The One-Class SVM has been used successfully in many areas, including text classification, face recognition, spam detection, anomaly detection, machine fault detection, among others [Khan and Madden 2014].

In [Tran et al. 2004] a network anomaly-based detector named OTAD is presented, which analyzes IP packets. This detector uses a fixed number of network features extracted with the tool *tcpstat*. OTAD uses an One-Class SVM classifier with RBF kernel to detect anomalies in network packets, employing a genetic algorithm to optimize the selection process for the classifier parameters. It is worth noting that this work uses a fixed number of features, while in our WAF this number depends on the number of parameters in the training data.

In [Perdisci et al. 2006], byte n -grams are extracted of the payload of network packets, a clustering algorithm is applied to reduce the number of features, which are the passed to an ensemble of One-Class SVMs to detect mimicry attacks.

The authors in [Parhizkar and Abadi 2015] extract a fixed number of features from HTTP requests and use an ensemble of One-Class SVMs to detect attacks in web traffic. Again, this work uses a fixed number of features, while our implementation extracts a variable number of features depending on the number of parameters in the training data.

The work in [Rieck 2009] proposed a network intrusion detector using a kind of One-Class SVM with RBF kernel to detect anomalies in HTTP and FTP traffic. They use numerical, sequential and syntactical features extracted from network payload. Their tests showed a good performance in detection and response time with respect to other state-of-art detection methods.

3. Fundamentals

This section provides fundamental notions about feature selection and the One-Class SVM classifier.

3.1. Feature Selection

Feature selection is the process in determining representative features from the original data; in our case the data corresponds to HTTP requests. Its aim is to obtain the appropriate features that represent regularities of the original dataset. This phase is fundamental for the success of classification algorithms and therefore for the anomalies detection process [Lim et al. 2007]. This process, in our case, can be view as functions that map the HTTP messages domain to a vectorial space \mathbb{R}^n , where $1 \leq n \leq \infty$.

Feature extraction can be done either manually, automatically or combining both of them. Many works rely on expert knowledge to define the list of most important features that truly represent the analyzed dataset (e.g. [Kruegel and Vigna 2003]). This list of features is very important because it allows to distinguish between normal and anomalous data. Other works are based on an automatic process, for example the *n-gram* analysis in [Wang and Stolfo 2004], although their results are less precise. In the works [Rieck 2009] and [Kloft et al. 2008] a third alternative is presented, which combines the two previous methods.

3.2. One-Class SVM

The One-Class SVM classifier is a special version of the well known SVM, proposed specifically to solve OCC problems [Schölkopf et al. 2001]. This classifier is trained with sample from only one class, the known class. Working on the assumption that all samples that do not belong to the training class are closer to the origin than to the training samples, during its training phase the One-Class SVM defines a hyperplane that separates the training samples from the origin [Khan and Madden 2014]. Sometimes the data can not be separated from the origin through a hyperplane in the original vector space; the One-Class SVM can use a transformation to a high-dimensional space in order to build its separating hyperplane [Parhizkar and Abadi 2015]. Equation 1 shows the formulation of this hyperplane; \vec{w} is the vector perpendicular to the hyperplane, ρ is the distance of the hyperplane to the origin and the function ϕ maps the samples from the original vector space to a higher dimensionality.

$$\vec{w} \cdot \phi(\vec{x}) - \rho = 0 \quad (1)$$

To obtain the optimal separating hyperplane, the One-Class SVM has to solve the optimization problem shown in Equation 2, subject to restrictions shown in Equation 3. Here, \vec{f}_i are the feature vectors of the training samples and ξ is the list of penalties incurred for any of the n training samples positioned on the same side of the hyperplane as the origin (these samples will not be recognized as belonging to the training class). The parameter ν is used to influence the amount of training samples that may be miss-classified in order to obtain an overall better placement of the hyperplane [Parhizkar and Abadi 2015].

$$\min_{\vec{w}, \rho, \xi} \frac{1}{2} \|\vec{w}\|^2 - \rho + \frac{1}{\nu n} \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{w} \cdot \phi(\vec{f}_i) \geq \rho - \xi_i, \quad \xi_i \geq 0, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

To avoid the immense computational cost of vector multiplication in the new high-dimensional space, the classifier may use a kernel function to simulate these multiplications at a lower cost. We employ the RBF kernel, which can be expressed as shown in Equation 4, where the parameter γ is used to determine the influence of the individual training samples for the position of the hyperplane [Rieck 2009].

$$K(\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2) = \phi(\vec{x}_1) \cdot \phi(\vec{x}_2) = \exp(-\gamma \|\vec{x}_1 - \vec{x}_2\|^2) \quad (4)$$

To take advantage of the low-cost kernel operations, the One-Class SVM may solve the dual formulation of the optimization problem, as shown in Equation 5, subject to the restrictions shown in Equation 6. Here, S is a matrix containing the multiplications of all training samples among themselves in the high-dimensional space (this can be replaced by low-cost kernel operations) and a is a vector of coefficients to be found by solving the dual formulation [Aggarwal 2013]. Training samples whose corresponding coefficient a_i is non-zero will be the support vectors of the trained classifier; this usually is only a small subset of samples of the training data [Perdisci et al. 2006].

$$\min_a \frac{1}{2} a S a^T \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^n a_i = 1, \quad 0 \leq a_i \leq \frac{1}{\nu n} \quad \forall j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

Finally, after completing the training phase, the One-Class SVM can use the hyperplane to classify new samples; only those separated from the origin by the hyperplane will be considered as belonging to the training class. This can be expressed as shown in Equation 7, where $g(\vec{x})$ is the decision function that returns +1 for samples belonging to the training class, while returning -1 for all other samples [Amer et al. 2013].

$$g(\vec{x}) = \begin{cases} \vec{w} \cdot \phi(\vec{x}) - \rho \geq 0 & +1 \\ \text{otherwise} & -1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Using the low-cost RBF kernel and the calculated coefficients a , this decision function can be expressed as shown in Equation 8; it needs to do calculations for the support vectors only, making $g(\vec{x})$ a fast and light operation to be used in the detection phase of the classifier [Perdisci et al. 2006].

$$g(\vec{x}) = \begin{cases} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(a_i \exp(-\gamma \|\vec{f}_i - \vec{x}\|^2) \right) - \rho \geq 0 & +1 \\ \text{otherwise} & -1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

4. Proposal

In this section, we describe the four main parts that make up our WAF, namely a routing step, a data preprocessing step, a classification step and lastly a response step. Our implementation was done in the programming language *Python* using the Machine Learning library *scikit-learn* and the code is accessible in our online repository under <https://github.com/nico-ralf-ii-fpuna/paper>.

4.1. Routing step

Since requests to the same URL show a greater similarity to each other than to requests to other URLs, our routing step groups the incoming requests by URL and HTTP method. This way during the training phase the anomaly models can be built independently for each group, resulting in a more precise description of the normal requests within each

group. Consequently, during the detection phase there are more accurate models of normal requests available, which help to identify requests that are anomalous within their corresponding groups, even though they would be considered normal in other groups.

4.2. Data preprocessing step

Our data preprocessing step extracts a vector of numeric features from each HTTP request, which is then passed to the classification step. We use feature extraction methods that yield a total of 10 numeric features. Four of our features indicate total length, number of digits, number of letters and number of non-alphanumeric characters. We based these on [Kruegel and Vigna 2003] and [Nguyen et al. 2011], adding some own extensions. Another five features, also based on [Kruegel and Vigna 2003], represent the bins of a method called character distribution. Our last feature represents the entropy according to Shannon [Dobrushin and Prelov 2011], an idea taken from [Nguyen et al. 2011]. The list of these features can be seen in Table 1.

Features	Range of results
Character distribution - bin 0	[0, 1]
Character distribution - bin 1	[0, 1]
Character distribution - bin 2	[0, 1]
Character distribution - bin 3	[0, 1]
Character distribution - bin 4	[0, 1]
Entropy	[0, ∞)
Length or total number of characters	[0, ∞)
Number of digits	[0, ∞)
Number of letters	[0, ∞)
Number of non-alphanumeric characters	[0, ∞)

Table 1. List of the 10 features extracted by our WAF from every analyzed value.

Our feature extraction methods are applied to the whole request, including HTTP method, URL, query string, headers, and body. Additionally, we employ the previously mentioned approach used in [Kruegel and Vigna 2003] and apply our extraction methods on each of the parameter values in the query string. We extend this approach to also analyze the parameter values in the body of the requests if there are any.

The obtained feature vector that represents a request will have $m \times (1+n)$ features. Here m is the number of features returned by our feature extraction methods for each value. The 1 represents the whole request and n is the number of parameters that are present in the query string and body. Its important to note that n might be different for each group of URL and HTTP method. During the training phase, all the different parameters from a group of requests are listed and given a fixed order for building the feature vector. This way, during the detection phase our WAF extracts the features of the values whose parameters have been seen in the training phase, assuring that their position within the vector is preserved. For example, if during training our WAF gets POST request which all have only the parameters *username* and *password* in its body, then $m = 10$ and $n = 2$, resulting in each request being represented by a vector of 30 features.

We are aware that our analysis of parameter values during the detection phase is only applied to parameters observed in training. This gives way to the risk of an intruder

including an attack inside the value of a previously unseen parameter. But since our feature extraction methods are also applied to the whole request, these attacks can still be detected and do not simply bypass our WAF.

4.3. Classification step

During the training phase, our WAF scales and normalizes the numeric feature vectors produced by the previous step and trains one One-Class SVM classifier for each group of URL and HTTP method. In this high dimensional vector space, the classifier tries to find boundaries to the regions in which the feature vectors of normal request reside, drawing these borders as tight as possible to exclude future vectors of anomalous requests, but loose enough to still include future normal requests not seen in the training phase [Perdisci et al. 2006]. This way the WAF obtains a model, a trained classifier, that generalizes the characteristics of normal HTTP requests within each group.

During the detection phase, the incoming requests are routed to their corresponding group, the feature extraction methods are applied and the trained classifier for that group checks if this new feature vector falls inside the established boundaries, marking it as normal if it does. All other requests will be denoted as anomalous.

The One-Class SVM takes a few parameters that influence its behavior. One of these parameters, denominated ν or ν , is used to set an upper bound to the fraction of training requests that may fall outside of the established boundaries. This gives the classifier some flexibility when drawing the borders in order to achieve higher generalization capabilities and also achieves robustness in case of some anomalies in the training data [Schölkopf et al. 2001]. Sometimes it can be difficult to find boundaries in the given vector space, so the classifier can use a so called kernel function to simulate a higher dimensionality in which it is easier to draw the separating borders. We tested three kernels, namely the linear, the polynomial and the *Radial Basis Function* (RBF) kernel. We obtained the best classification results with the last one. The RBF kernel also has a parameter called *gamma* or γ that influences the shape of the boundaries [Tran et al. 2004].

4.4. Response step

Our WAF can be configured to respond in different ways to the classification results. If a request is considered normal, it is forwarded to its intended destination. Otherwise, the WAF logs the result and optionally can also block that request, preventing possible attacks from reaching the applications. Our implementation could be extended, for example, to send alarms about anomalies to the people responsible for the system.

5. Experiments and results

For the quantitative evaluation of the performance of our WAF, we used the public data sets CSIC 2010 [Torrano-Giménez et al. 2010] and CSIC TORPEDA 2012 [Torrano-Giménez et al. 2012], which contain labeled HTTP requests to an e-commerce web application. Given that our WAF groups the requests by URL and HTTP method, we grouped the requests from both data sets by these criteria and selected those groups that had more than 100 samples of each of the two categories, normal and anomalous. This left us with 18 groups, totaling 40,130 normal and 42,444 anomalous HTTP requests.

5.1. Detection effectiveness test

In a first test, we used the aforementioned data to measure the detection effectiveness of our WAF. To demonstrate the added value of analyzing the parameter values, we tested two different scenarios. Firstly, we applied our feature extraction methods only to the whole request, obtaining a fixed number of 10 features. Secondly, we included the analysis of parameter values, yielding different number of features for each group, as described in the previous section. Additionally, for the selection of ν and γ for each group, we tested values in the range $[0.0001 : 0.1]$ and chose those that gave the best result in each group. Table 2 shows average and standard deviation of true positive rate (TPR), false positive rate (FPR) and F_1 score of our results. F_1 score uses the number of true positives (TP), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN), and it is expressed as $F_1 = \frac{2TP}{2TP+FP+FN}$, where values closer to 1 indicate better results.

Scenario	average TPR	average FPR	average F_1	best F_1
using only the whole request	0.91 ± 0.11	0.31 ± 0.34	0.82 ± 0.18	1.00
including parameter analysis	0.95 ± 0.05	0.09 ± 0.11	0.93 ± 0.07	1.00

Table 2. Results of detection effectiveness test for all 18 groups

Our results show that the second scenario improves the overall detection, with TPR and F_1 raising from 0.91 and 0.82 to 0.95 and 0.93 respectively and FPR lowering from 0.31 to 0.09, even though both scenarios have groups that achieve a perfect score. These results demonstrate the usefulness of including the analysis of parameter values.

5.2. Response time analysis

Our second test aimed to quantify the effects our WAF has on the response time of the web applications it protects. To that end, we set up a simple application and measured the response time in three different scenarios; in one the requests went directly to the application, in the second the traffic was routed through our WAF but with detection disabled, and in the third scenario with enabled detection. The second and third scenarios show an increase of 2 and 4 ms respectively when compared to the scenario without the WAF. This delay is only a small increase compared to the overall roundtrip time of HTTP traffic, so our WAF should not have noticeable effects on the response time.

5.3. Training time analysis

In our third test, we analyzed how the training time of our WAF relates to the amount of requests used. Since groups may have different durations because of an unequal number of features, the highest numbers give an upper bound. We observed that the time per request stays close to 2 ms in our test setup with 10,000 requests. Our numbers show that the training time has an almost linear relationship to the amount of training data.

5.4. Comparisons with others works

Table 3 shows detection performance comparison with other works that use the CSIC 2010 dataset, the same dataset that we employ. We find that in [Parhizkar and Abadi 2015] a TPR of 0.96 and a FPR of 0.03 is reported for the ensemble of One-Class SVMs. The popular *misuse-based* WAFs, ModSecurity ¹, were used

¹www.modsecurity.org

with default rules on the first data set, CSIC 2010, obtaining a TPR of only 0.55 without false positives and with a F1-Score of 0.71 [Giménez and Cappo 2015], significantly lower than the results we achieved with our WAF. The work in [Torrano-Giménez 2015] does not report the F1-score only TPR and FPR.

Reference	Observations	TPR	FPR	F ₁ -score
This work	OC-SVM with variable number of <i>features</i>	0.93	0.03	0.95
<i>ModSecurity</i> [Giménez and Cappo 2015]	Popular signature-based WAF	0.56	0.00	0.71
Torrano-Giménez [Torrano-Giménez 2015]	Average of four distinct decision tree	0.95	0.05	-
Parhizkar y Abadi (<i>OC-WAD</i>)	OC-SVM with fixed number of <i>features</i>	0.96	0.03	-

Table 3. Detection comparison with other works that use CSIC 2010 dataset

6. Conclusions

The WAF we present in this article uses the One-Class SVM classifier to tackle the task of detecting anomalous HTTP requests in order to protect web applications from possible attacks. Following and extending the ideas obtained from other authors, we built feature extraction methods that take advantage of the structure of HTTP requests, specifically the values of individual parameters, to represent these requests with vectors which contain more useful information. Our tests show a significant improvement in the detection results when including the analysis of parameter values. Furthermore, our implementation shows that it is fast enough to be used as a WAF, even though the minimization of the processing time was not our primary goal and further optimizations could be made.

One contribution of our paper is the adaptation and extension of the parameter value analysis presented in [Kruegel and Vigna 2003]. The anomaly models employed by the cited authors do not produce numeric vectors for each request, and so we adapted them to make feature extraction methods that are useful for Machine Learning tools, in our case specifically the One-Class SVM. As another contribution, we leave a link in Section 4 to the online repository that contains the code of our implementation, which includes the WAF and the tests mentioned in this paper, so that other authors can reproduce our results and have a starting point for further research.

Future works could look into finding additional features to detect anomalous requests. Another research area is other classification tools to be used instead of the One-Class SVM to tackle the OCC task. Additionally, our work lacks automatic selection of the values for ν and γ of the classifier and further inquiries can be made in that direction.

References

Aggarwal, C. C. (2013). *Outlier Analysis*. Springer Publishing Company, Incorporated.

- Amer, M., Goldstein, M., and Abdennadher, S. (2013). Enhancing one-class support vector machines for unsupervised anomaly detection. In *Proceedings of the ACM SIGKDD Workshop on Outlier Detection and Description*. ACM.
- Dobrushin, R. and Prelov, V. (2011). Entropy - encyclopedia of mathematics. <http://www.encyclopediaofmath.org/index.php?title=Entropy&oldid=15099>. Accessed: August-2017.
- Giménez, J. and Cappo, C. (2015). Http-ws-ad: Anomaly detector oriented to web applications and services. In *Computing Conference (CLEI), 2015 Latin American*. IEEE.
- Khan, S. and Madden, M. (2014). One-class classification: taxonomy of study and review of techniques. *The Knowledge Engineering Review*, 29(3):345–374.
- Kloft, M., Brefeld, U., Düessel, P., Gehl, C., and Laskov, P. (2008). Automatic feature selection for anomaly detection. In *Proceedings of the 1st ACM workshop on Workshop on AISec*, pages 71–76. ACM.
- Kruegel, C. and Vigna, G. (2003). Anomaly detection of web-based attacks. In *Proceedings of the 10th ACM conference on Computer and communications security*. ACM.
- Kruegel, C., Vigna, G., and Robertson, W. (2005). A multi-model approach to the detection of web-based attacks. *Computer Networks*, 48(5).
- Lim, S. H., Wang, L.-L., and DeJong, G. (2007). Explanation-based feature construction. In *IJCAI*, volume 7, pages 931–936.
- Nguyen, H. T., Torrano-Gimenez, C., Alvarez, G., Petrović, S., and Franke, K. (2011). Application of the generic feature selection measure in detection of web attacks. In *Computational Intelligence in Security for Information Systems*, pages 25–32. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.
- Parhizkar, E. and Abadi, M. (2015). Oc-wad: A one-class classifier ensemble approach for anomaly detection in web traffic. In *2015 23rd Iranian Conference on Electrical Engineering (ICEE)*, pages 631–636. IEEE.
- Perdisci, R., Gu, G., and Lee, W. (2006). Using an ensemble of one-class svm classifiers to harden payload-based anomaly detection systems. In *Data Mining, 2006. ICDM'06. Sixth International Conference on*, pages 488–498. IEEE.
- Rieck, K. (2009). *Machine learning for application-layer intrusion detection*. PhD thesis, Technischen Universität Berlin. Accessible under: <http://dx.doi.org/10.14279/depositonce-2199>.
- Schölkopf, B., Platt, J. C., Shawe-Taylor, J., Smola, A. J., and Williamson, R. C. (2001). Estimating the support of a high-dimensional distribution. *Neural computation*, 13(7):1443–1471.
- Torrano-Giménez, C. (2015). *Study of stochastic and machine learning techniques for anomaly-based web attack detection*. PhD thesis, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.
- Torrano-Giménez, C., Pérez, A., and Álvarez, G. (2012). Csic torpeda 2012 http data sets. <http://www.tic.itefi.csic.es/torpeda>. Accessed: July-2017.
- Torrano-Giménez, C., Pérez Villegas, A., and Álvarez Marañón, G. (2010). Csic 2010 http data sets. <http://www.isi.csic.es/dataset/>. Accessed: July-2017.

Tran, Q.-A., Duan, H., and Li, X. (2004). One-class support vector machine for anomaly network traffic detection. *China Education and Research Network (CERNET), Tsinghua University, Main Building*, 310.

Wang, K. and Stolfo, S. J. (2004). Anomalous payload-based network intrusion detection. In *RAID*, volume 4, pages 203–222. Springer.